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Pavement Dwellers of Kolkata: A Geographical Description

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Homelessness is a burning issue of the whole world as in almost every country there is a sizeable number of homeless people. They are undernourished, prone to different types of diseases, mostly illiterate or little literate and socially and economically marginalised with little to no access of the basic living facilities. This issue is more critical in the populous nations of the third world. This paper attempts to investigate the issues and challenges related to the pavement dwellers of Kolkata, one of the most populous cities in India. This study selected 210 pavement dwelling groups/ so called households, consisting of 534 individuals for field observation as the primary data, based on a structured questionnaire and used secondary data of the various census reports and reports published by the Kolkata Metropolitan Development Authority (KMDA). This study reveals about the trend of immigration and the demographic, economic, educational, health and hygienic status of these targeted community. It also reveals that the duration of the dwelling on the pavements has a keen relationship with the occupation type of these people. With the assessment of the overall conditions, there are a number of approaches, given here, could be taken to improve the lives of the homeless people.

Keywords: *Pavement dwellers, Socio-economic condition, Push-pull factors, Homelessness*

I. INTRODUCTION

For the survival of people three basic needs are food, clothing and shelter; but many in the world do not have these. Now-a-days this has achieved a global concern as the urban areas of almost the whole world are characterized by such people. We may call it a result of the capitalist society. The rootlessness is mainly caused by natural or political phenomenon or by the ill and unsuited economic systems. Various push-pull factors force people to live their lives under the sky and on the pavements.

Kolkata is the one of the most populous city in India having a huge pressure of population. According to the Census of 2011, Kolkata has around 70,000 pavement

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dwellers, who have to stay under the flyovers, on the footpaths and do their daily activity without curtains. These people face many problems in various aspects like identification, nutrition, health, education, sanitation, income etc. "Sometimes they have to offer bribes or other kind of services to the shop keepers, local power leader or police to allow them to stay on the road" (Ghosh, 2014; Adhikari, 2014). But these people are also important as they form a considerable percentage of the total population and form an active part of the socio-economy of Kolkata. "Regardless of the reasons for people living on the street, street dwelling can create specific problems, such as crime and other antisocial activities, including prostitution, begging and drug abuse" (Anam, 1997; Ray, 2001).

This descriptive study is an attempt to look through the lifestyle of the pavement dwellers, their demographic and socio-economic condition and also their nutrition and health related issues and their involvement with the socio-political aspect. This study will further suggest areas towards which policy or relief could be directed.

II. OBJECTIVES

The primary objectives of this study are-

- i. To find out the factors that are pulling the people from different districts and states of India to Kolkata.
- ii. To assess the socio-economic and demographic condition of the homeless people of Kolkata along with their problems.
- iii. To find out how the duration of living on the pavement is being changed over the occupation.
- iv. To find out the status of infrastructure and amenities, education, health and hygiene of the pavement dwellers of Kolkata.
- v. To suggest areas in which policy or relief could be directed towards.

III. LOCATION OF THE STUDY AREA

Kolkata is located in the eastern part of India having extension of 22°82'N latitude and 88°20'E longitude. It is spreading linearly along the bank of the River Hugli. The city stands at an average elevation of 6.5 m above Mean Sea Level with a slope towards east. Kolkata Municipal Corporation (KMC) is of a total area of 185 km² and is divided into 15 boroughs and 141 wards. Homeless people are found in 118 wards only, and the rest 23 wards are free of them. Maximum concentration of these houseless people is found in and around the Central Business District area.

LOCATION MAP OF THE STUDY AREA

Source: Map no. 1,2,3 have been collected from Google Maps and prepared by the author using QGIS Software, version 4.3. Map no. 4 has been prepared using Google Earth (Accessed on 01/04/2020) by the author.

This study is based on the data of the Homeless people who are compelled to make the footpaths of various parts of Kolkata as their Home. The study area has been segmented into North Kolkata, Central Kolkata and South Kolkata.

The 25 places and pavements of the homeless people, where the survey has been conducted randomly are as follows -

- i) **North Kolkata:** Shovabazar, Shyambazar, B.T. Road, Paikpara, Belgachia, Hazra More and Mahatma Gandhi Road and Girish Park
- ii) **Central Kolkata:** New Market, Sudder Street, College Street, Surya Sen Street, Amherst Street, Chandni Chowk, Esplanade, Sealdah and Central Avenue.

- iii) **South Kolkata:** Ballygunge Phari, Gariahat More, Golpark, Southern Avenue, Park Street, CIT Road, Mallick Bazar, Rash Behari Avenue and Central Avenue.

IV. DATA SOURCE AND METHODOLOGY

In this paper primary as well as secondary data have been used. Primary data have been collected from the extensive field survey undertaken, from 9th to 15th September 2019, in various places of Kolkata, where pavement dwellers can be found. The survey covered 210 dwelling groups or so called households, containing 534 individuals. The random sampling method was followed in the direct face to face interview. As the pavement dwellers are not available/ cannot be identified during daytime, the survey was done at night after 8:30 pm. The survey combined quantitative as well as qualitative methods and the data were collected by a structured questionnaire that pertained to basic socio-economic and health and hygiene indicators. Informal interviews have also been used to collect qualitative data. Various reports of Kolkata Metropolitan Development Authority (KMDA) and the Census of India have been collected and used as secondary data. To get the conceptual knowledge framework of the study various journals and research papers also have been consulted. Different statistical and cartographic techniques have been used for representation of the various data, in this paper. GIS and GPS techniques are also used for mapping and plotting survey points respectively.

V. HOMELESS PEOPLE: SCENARIO OF INDIA AND WEST BENGAL

From 1961 to 1981 the number of homeless people increased rapidly caused by the immigration from East Pakistan (Present Bangladesh). After 1991 the total number is slowly decreasing but in 2011, 1.77 million people still live in streets, accounting for 0.15 percent of the country's total population (Table-I). Number of homeless people in the rural areas has decreased by 28 percent whereas the urban areas have reported a 20 percent increase from 2001 to 2011. Nearly 26 percent of the homeless population in urban India lives in the top five metros (Kumuda, 2014), whereas 65.3 percent is

Table I
Homeless Population of India (Lakhs)

<i>Year</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Rural</i>	<i>Urban</i>
1961	11.65	9.7	1.95
1971	19.86	15.2	4.66
1981	23.43	17.24	6.19
1991	20.07	12.82	7.25
2001	19.44	11.65	7.89
2011	17.72	8.34	9.38

Source: Different Census Reports

spread over the six states of India: Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Gujarat and Andhra Pradesh.

7.78 percent of India's total homeless population i.e. 134,040, live in West Bengal comprising 68.52 percent male and 31.48 percent female. The highest population of the homeless people, that is 52.07 percent of the state's total, has been found in the capital city, Kolkata, followed by North 24 Pgs. (6.81 percent), North Dinajpur (6.16 percent), Howrah (4.25 percent), South 24 Pgs. (4.06 percent) and Barddhaman (3.77 percent) (Table: II)

Table II
Distribution of Homeless Population (District Wise) of West Bengal, 2011

Name of the district	Number	Share in State's total	Rank	Name of the district	Number	Share in State's total	Rank
Kolkata	69798	52.07	1	Nadia	2957	2.21	11
N. 24 Pgs	9122	6.81	2	Birbhum	2917	2.18	12
N. Dinajpur	8251	6.16	3	Jalpaiguri	1924	1.44	13
Haora	5699	4.25	4	Bankura	1925	1.44	14
S. 24 Pgs	5436	4.06	5	E. Midnapore	1720	1.28	15
Barddhaman	5057	3.77	6	Purulia	1587	1.18	16
Hugli	3969	2.96	7	Darjeeling	1559	1.16	17
W. Midnapore	3768	2.81	8	S. Dinajpur	868	0.65	18
Murshidabad	3460	2.58	9	Cooch Behar	700	0.52	19
Maldah	3323	2.48	10	West Bengal	134040	100	

Source: Census of India, 2011

VI. HOMELESS PEOPLE: SCENARIO OF KOLKATA

Kolkata started its journey in 1960 with the amalgamation of three villages- Sutanati, Gobingapur and Kalikata. Within a very short period it grew into a principal centre of economy, culture and administration used mainly by the colonial rulers and flourished to attract millions of skilled and unskilled labourers from the adjoining districts and states and resulted in a huge population increase from 0.8 million in 1911 to 4.49 million in 2011. "Such large scale international migration along with changing cause, character, scale and impact turned Kolkata from the 'city of migrants' to the 'city of refugees' in the post independent era" (Chatterjee, 1990). "Nearly six million refugees have come over to West Bengal in different waves up to 1971 and nearly 2 million refugees used to reside in Calcutta Municipal District Area in 1973 which constitutes almost 26 percent of the total population" (CMDA 1976, Som 1987).

"In absence of proper historical records on pavement dwelling in the city, estimation about the actual figure of those people is really difficult. They were recorded as 'houseless people' in the Census and without any 'residence' numbers" (Mukherjee, 1975). "However, exact identification of pavement dwellers is almost impossible owing

to their shifting character of residence combined with their fear for eviction by the civic authorities” (Roy Chowdhury, 1999). A survey reveals that the total number of pavement dwellers was 48,802 in 1971, 34,316 in 1980-81 and 55,571 in 1987; out of which 55,005 were residing within the old Calcutta Corporation Area (KMDA, 1987; Jagannathan and Halder, 1988; Mukherjee, 1975). Now the number of houseless people is 69,798, which comprises 1.55 percent of the total population who have no permanent house and compelled to live on the streets, under the open sky (Census, 2011).

Figure 1
Decadal Growth of Homeless People

Source: Different Census Reports

6.1 Trend of Immigration

A huge population migrated to Kolkata from East Pakistan (Presently Bangladesh) for nearly four decades, from the partition of British India up to the creation of independent Bangladesh. People also migrated from surrounding districts like Nadia, Murshidabad, Birbhum, North and South 24 Parganas, East and West Midnapore etc. and from the neighbouring states like Jharkhand, Bihar, Orissa, Uttar Pradesh and even from Gujarat. Figure-2, prepared on the surveyed population (September, 2019), represents the trend of immigration from different states to Kolkata.

Figure 2
Trend of Immigration (from different states to Kolkata) of the Surveyed Population

Source: Primary Data

6.2 Causes of Immigration and Homelessness

A large number of people have emigrated from Bangladesh (Former East Pakistan) because of the unstable political scenario in the 80s. After that many people immigrated

because of job opportunity and better socio-economic factors. Surplus labour in agricultural sector, landlessness and less job opportunity worked as push-pull factors. Some other causes also found like: Some have physical or mental disability, some have lost homes when their husband died, and some women were thrown out when they gave birth to girl child. These people are compelled to stay on the streets as they are unable to take a house on rent. Some of them may afford rent but did not have the initial capital to pay the high security deposit.

6.3 Age-Sex Composition

According to the Census 2011, within this 69,798 people 78.30 percent are male and 21.69 percent are female. During the last decade 2001 to 2011, male population has increased from 51,531 to 54,658 and the female population has decreased from 16,145 to 15,140. "Presence of the significant size of single male people indicates the male dominance among migrants, following the age-sex selective nature of migration. Despite the fact, presence of significant share of child population indicates that families constitute the major demographic group among them" (Jaganathan and Halder, 1989).

Among the total respondents male population is 376 and female population is 158 by percent it is 70.41 and 29.59 respectively. By the following diagrammatic representation (Figure 4 and 5) we can easily understand the Age-Sex composition of the respondent people.

Figure 3
Age-Sex Composition of the Pavement Dwellers (1951-2011)

Source: Different Census Reports

Figure 4
Sex Composition of Sample

Figure 5
Age Distribution of Sample

Source: Primary Data

6.4 Duration of Living on the Pavements, Occupation and Income

Forty different types of occupation have been found here including various small jobs, low-end menial work and diverse services. During the physical survey it has been seen that the duration of living on the pavements is different and it changes over their occupation. People, coming from different districts and those who are engaged in the selling of various kinds of toys, doormat, hand fan etc. usually stay for only one night on the pavement. People who are engaged in the selling of various craft items and begging, usually stay for a week and the people working as musicians at band party, seasonal labours (those usually work under contractors), seller of various kinds of decorative works, earthen idols etc. usually like to stay for a month. People who are engaged with van delivery, rickshaw pulling, rag picking, cooking, mending shoes, fish selling, running small shops or working as a porter and day labour are compelled to stay on the pavements permanently. Table-3 depicts the picture of the durational change of dwelling on the pavements based on occupation.

Table 3
The Duration of Living on The Pavements based on Occupation

Sl. No.	Duration of Dwelling on Pavements	Occupation
1	One night's Dwellers	Toy selling, Doormat selling, Hand fan selling etc.
2	One week's Dwellers	Begging, Craft item Seller etc.
3	Month long dwellers	Playing music at band party, Seasonal labour, decorative item, earthen idols etc. selling
4	Permanent Dwellers	Van delivery, Rag picking, Cooking, Day labour, Vending, Rickshaw pulling, Mending shoes, Fish selling, Running small shops, Porter etc.

Source: Primary Data

There is a lot of range within intra-occupation incomes as well as inter-occupation incomes. Even within the same occupation there is a lot of difference in income in different places. It is also important to observe the link between gender and occupation. Most van pullers, cooks, cobblers, day labourers, and rickshaw pullers were predominately men while most rag pickers and domestic helps are usually women. They're almost as many men as women who beg. In the sample, 13.1 percent of all pavement dwellers within the working ages 18-60 are unemployed. 10.8 percent of all children between the ages of 5 and 15 were working. The most common occupation in this age group is begging, that is 63 percent of the surveyed population. Average daily income is highest in the occupation of cooking, that is around Rupees 175 and the lowest is in Rag Picking, that is Rupees 68.

From primary data it has been found that nearly 51 percent of the surveyed population earn Rupees 150-200 per day, whereas another 7 percent families earn less than Rupees 100 per day. The entire amount, earned by them, is spent to sustain their daily life. In this critical situation all the members of the family are forced or compelled to work for extra income in whatever way it may be. It has also been observed that daily per capita income is different in different places. In Howrah, Armenium Ghat and Amherst Street seem to have the lowest average incomes. We can also see high incomes in Esplanade, as it is a part of the core of the Central Business District (CBD) of Kolkata.

It has been also observed that the majority did not change any job in last six months. Only 7.6 percent of the surveyed population, have changed their job in last six months. It has been found that job changing is more evident in the lower income groups.

Table 3

Showing the Inter-Occupational Average Daily Income (in Rupees) of The Surveyed Population

<i>Occupation</i>	<i>Van delivery</i>	<i>Begging</i>	<i>Cook</i>	<i>Cobbler</i>	<i>Day labour</i>	<i>Rickshaw Pulling</i>	<i>Hawker</i>	<i>Driving</i>	<i>Fish selling</i>	<i>Rag Picking</i>
Average Income/day	166.2	61.1	173.5	102.1	150.2	153.9	125.2	136.5	156.6	68.2

Source: Primary Data

6.5 Infrastructure and Amenities

“The pavement dwellers of Kolkata are forced to live on the pavements, open verandas, under bridges, railway platforms, abandoned large pipes, courtyards of religious places and even hand carts they pull in daytime to earn their living” (Jagannathan and Haldar,1988). Throughout the year change in weather as well as the change in temperature and rainfall affects their living,. Street lights can light their surroundings but not their lives. They quench their thirst from the taps on the streets. They are under

the constant threat of being evicted as they are not legally allowed to set up structures on the pavements. Tarpaulins or plastics, blankets, warm clothes, mobile phones, bedding and mattress, mosquito nets, stoves and cooking utensils and mobile phones are the physical assets of these people. Within the surveyed population around 67 percent of the households have the required warm clothes and only 46 percent have a bed or mattress to sleep on it. Only 32.7 percent of the households have cooking utensils while only 21.5 percent households possess a mosquito net. 52.8 percent of the households possess a mobile phone and 2.5 percent possess a radio.

It is found that only 15 percent of the total surveyed population have a bank account and having a bank account does not necessarily imply that these people actually use them. Out of the people, who have a bank account, only 37.5 percent have saved money and 29.1 percent have taken credit. From the following diagram, one can easily understand about the amenities of these pavement dwellers.

Fig 6
Status of Household Amenities

Source: Primary Data

Fig 7
Possession of Bank Account of the Surveyed Population

Source: Primary Data

6.6 Food and Cooking

The food habit of the pavement dwellers of Kolkata fluctuates with their rate of income. Questions like ‘normal diet’ and ‘number of times of taking food per day’ are far from their reality. Typically, the pavement dweller lived frugally, with just one or two changes of clothes, and a slim bedding; for families a few pots and pans, and a cheap stove were additions to the asset base. Most respondents, i.e. around 54.45 percent of the total surveyed population, reported eating two meals a day, although among the absolute destitute one meal (12.25 percent) and half a meal per day was also common. The food they usually have is either purchased from cheap restaurants or cooked in family kitchens, which are (usually made by three bricks) located on the roadside. A typical meal is a plate of rice with dal and some potatoes that costs around Rupees 20. Sometimes when they have a little more to spend, they include fish and egg with that. Chicken is also included once in a month which is nothing but wastage to them. They like to collect food from temples and mosques for a saving. Sometimes excess food from rich people’s houses, brought by the women working as a cook, satisfy their hunger. As the pavement dwellers do not possess permanent places to live and they are ready to move from place to place, their kitchen system is also irregular.

Fig 8
Types of Fuel Used by The Surveyed Population

Source: Primary Data

Fig 9
No. of Meals Taken/ Day by the Respondents

Source: Primary Data

It has been found that amongst the people who are able to cook food in the streets a large majority use wood (64 percent) in smoky 'chulas'. The next most preferred fuel is kerosene oil (24 percent). The most unpopular fuel is coal (5 percent) and the rest (7 percent) use both kerosene and wood.

6.7 Educational Attainment

In India, Kolkata is well known as an educational and cultural hub but the educational level of the pavement dwellers of Kolkata is very poor. Amidst starvation and prolonged hunger, manifestation of perfection through education is an embarrassing query to a pavement dwelling family anywhere across the world. Families which wonder what to eat the next day are forced to send their children to beg near traffic signals or work as child labour in any shop nearby (Dey and Majumder, 2015). From the survey, it has been revealed that only 40.26 percent of the total surveyed people are literate and 59.74 percent people are illiterate. Gender bias has been observed in the school-going children. Male child is sent to school over the female child and they are given better opportunity than female child. It has been revealed that parents are willing to make their daughters as a helping hand either in their occupation or in the household work. A huge number of dropouts have been noticed among the pavement dwellers. The main cause of the school drop-outs is poor economy. Almost half of the dropout students are affected by this. The other causes with their respective statistics are given in the following figure.

Fig 10
Literacy Rate of The Surveyed Population

Source: Primary Data

Fig 11
Causes of School Dropout of the Respondents

Source: Primary Data

6.8 Health and Hygiene

Like the other urban areas, pavement dwellers of Kolkata often face the worst of urban problems like low sanitation and pollution. They face the ugly side of the intense production activity of the city. They live in surroundings that are hazardous and unfit for a healthy lifestyle. Because of the state government and the KMDA's initiatives

for setting up the 'Pay and Use Toilets', these are available all around the Kolkata for the pavement dwellers. They have a complaint of distant location and rising charge of using 'Pay and Use Toilets'. Around 90 percent of the surveyed people use these only for latrine in the day time when the roads are busy. But after the sunset they use the open places to stop 'wasting' their money.

It has been found that these people take medicines from the medical shop without taking any advice from a doctor as they think visiting a doctor is a luxury. It has also been found that 38.2 percent of total surveyed population had gone for a medical check-up in the last six months. Almost 39 percent of the surveyed population use some form of contraception. Male contraceptives like condoms are more popular with slightly more affluent households. Poorer households, on the other hand, use more of female contraceptives. Less than 30 percent woman use some form of contraception.

It has been found that a vast majority of the homeless female population use a piece of cotton or worn clothes instead of sanitary pads as this has still remained a luxury good for them. Only 17 percent of the surveyed female population use sanitary pads.

6.9 Addictions

From the survey it has been revealed that more than 70 percent of the total surveyed group/ household had at least one person with a harmful addiction. It has been found that tobacco products including smoke-able items like Cigarette, 'Hookah' (Chillum) and 'Biri' (Beedis) and smokeless items like 'Khaini', 'Gutka', 'Paan Masala' etc. are taken as the substance of addiction by 84 percent of the total surveyed people, within these 'Khaini' is the most popular. Sometimes alcohol is also taken by these people (16 percent), occasionally.

Fig 12
Addiction Substances of The Surveyed Population

Source: Primary Data

6.10 Suggestions

After looking at both quantitative and qualitative data some suggestions can be made that need to be done as soon as possible to improve the overall situation of the pavement dwellers of Kolkata.

- i. Identification of pavement dwellers and provision of voter IDs and Ration Cards: It has been found that only 44 percent of the total surveyed target population, above the age of 18, had a voter ID. The first immediate action to be taken is to identify those pavement dwellers that do not possess a Voter ID card, and provide the same to bring them into the mainstream of the society and to save them from various kinds of harassments and help them availing the privileges from the government. Bringing these socially and economically marginalised people under the Public Distribution System (PDS) providing the ration cards will help them to satisfy hunger and this will eradicate various unsocial and antisocial activities like begging, thieving etc.
- ii. Organise regular health camp and set up more toilets: It has been seen that most of the target population is unaware of their health. Regular health camps have to be organised to maintain their health status and to create health awareness through group counselling. Pavement dwellers mostly do not use 'Pay and Use' toilets to prevent 'wastage' of money. Government as well as Non-Government Organizations should take initiatives regarding this matter.
- iii. Rehabilitation: The people, coming from distant places, districts, states, that are engaged in selling of various kinds of items are compelled to stay on the pavements for a night or a week. Open markets can be opened up in various places where accommodation facility is also available. Contractors can provide temporary settlement to the labourers for the duration of work. The Central Government as well as the State Government can take a long term policy to rehabilitate these pavement dwellers by spreading infrastructure. KMDA can take positive steps to rehabilitate those who live on the pavements permanently.
- iv. Way out to a permanent income: By providing proper job-oriented training, setting up various types of cottage industries, Govt. or NGOs can drive away the curse of unemployment and marginal income. Govt. has to create employment opportunities in villages and small towns to stop migration. State and local Govt. can take initiatives to employ these people in various construction projects such as building and repairing roads, highways, buildings etc.
- v. Understand the depth and nature of the crisis, and test innovative developmental policies: A large-scale study should be undertaken by the state as well as the NGOs, using randomisation or complete enumeration to pin point the most pressing problems. Extensive studies to be undertaken to reveal progress and conditions of the ongoing projects and initiatives. Using the findings, the state needs to recalibrate its developmental policy to become sensitive to the factors which have been often overlooked.

VII. CONCLUSION

Modernisation and beautification of the city can make the cities beautiful but the harsh cruelties of life cannot be ignored after one gains an insight into the lives of the pavement dwellers, who are facing numerous problems that are related to the basic needs of life. The invisible population or the ghost people are considered as illegal encroachers and are charged against their illegal congestion by the urban administrative authority and the elite class residents as well as the pedestrians. The homeless people of Kolkata are in the worst condition. They have to stay under the flyovers, on the footpaths and do their daily activity without curtains. These people face many problems in various aspects like identification, nutrition, health, education, sanitation, income etc. They are being ill-treated and underestimated by the mainstream section of society. The administrative machinery have to pay proper attention to mitigate the problems faced by this excluded community and provide security and facilities for the betterment of their life and bring them in the mainstream of society.

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